

DESORPTION OF IMMOBILIZED *ESHERICHIA COLI* CELLS, *PCS. ATCC 25922* WITH SOLID ADSORBENTS CREATED WITH VARIOUS FORMS OF ALUMINUM OXIDE

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Abstract. *The work presents data obtained on the desorption of Escherichia coli, pcs. ATCC 25922, immobilized on various solid supports, created by micro-arc oxidation of aluminum formed on the surface of a ceramic coating: ZnAl, AMg6, D16. The stages and degrees of elution of adsorbed bacterial cells on solid alumina supports using 0.5 M NaCl are shown depending on the pH, time and volume of elution. Efficient desorption was observed for ZnAl sorbent, reaching up to 74.36% after 10 times elution within 50 minutes. The desorption of immobilized bacterial cells on the AMg6 carrier was 66.77%; in the D16 carrier, the number of desorbed cells was 61.11%. The results obtained on the desorption of immobilized cells of the bacterium Escherichia coli using 0.5 M NaCl showed different results depending on the carriers, frequency and volume of elution.*

Keywords: *solid sorbents, bacteria, immobilization, degrees of adsorption, desorption, time, volumes, elution efficiency, cells, desorption assessment.*

INTRODUCTION. The immobilization of cells and enzymes is a widespread natural phenomenon that plays a crucial role in survival strategies and the preservation of maximum catalytic functions. Naturally occurring cell aggregates can be regarded as immobilized cells. The biofilms formed in this process, incorporating cells within them, serve as highly efficient catalysts for various detrimental processes, such as the biocorrosion of metal structures, the degradation of plastic materials, and the onset of inflammatory processes, among others. Therefore, insoluble materials to which a particular type of cell (or enzyme) naturally adheres (e.g., wood, soil, wool, minerals, etc.) are often used as carriers. In such cases, the functioning of the immobilized cell (or enzyme) occurs naturally [1].

The principle of immobilization involves stabilizing the enzymatic activity of cells (or enzymes), significantly increasing volumetric productivity, broadening the pH and temperature optima, extending the lifespan of enzymes both inside and outside the cell, reducing process time, and achieving a more efficient conversion of substrate into the desired product instead of biomass formation [2–8].

The use of insoluble carriers for the immobilization of cells and enzymes allows for the production of a contaminant-free product while enabling multiple reuses and the technically simple separation of the system from reagents [9]. It is known that certain factors influence the ability of cells and enzymes to attach to solid carriers, though their direct interactions have not yet been fully

studied. The chemical composition, charge, and hydrophobicity of the surface, as well as the enzyme's age and the cell's growth phase, significantly affect the ability of cells and enzymes to adhere to the carrier. Other important factors include the physicochemical properties of the carrier surface, the pH, and the ionic strength of the medium. The attachment of cells to the carrier can be enhanced by adding molecules that modify the properties of cell walls [5].

The efficiency of a biocatalyst is largely determined by how effectively immobilized cells (or enzymes) are supplied with nutrients or substrates and how easily metabolites are removed. These factors mainly depend on diffusion barriers created by the carrier material [10].

One of the ways to increase the productivity of continuous microbiological processes and achieve high cell culture density is through the use of immobilized cells. These cells retain their proliferative function both after immobilization and after desorption, allowing for long-term use in biotechnological processes. At the same time, the kinetic growth characteristics (specific growth rate and doubling time) of immobilized cells do not significantly differ from those of free cells [1]. Another key characteristic distinguishing immobilized cells from free cells is their prolonged functional activity [8].

It has been suggested that the carrier acts as a protective barrier for immobilized cells, "shielding" them from the harmful effects of metabolites and preventing their penetration into the matrix. However, according to the findings of E.N. Efremenko, the carrier matrix does not hinder the penetration of even high-molecular-weight compounds such as DNA into the cells [1].

Traditionally, both inorganic and organic adsorbents are used as carriers for microorganism immobilization [8]. The advantages of inorganic carriers include their wide availability and low cost, high mechanical strength, excellent thermal stability, resistance to organic solvents and microbial degradation, ease of use, and renewability [11]. Commonly used inorganic carriers for immobilization include palygorskite, montmorillonite, mica, diatomite, porous porcelain, ground pumice, glass beads, porous glass, ceramic carriers, wood chips, cellulose fibers and its derivatives, activated charcoal, synthetic polymers, and others [2, 4, 12-14].

Additionally, using matrices such as alginate, pectate, carrageenan, chitosan, agar, and synthetic polymers (polyacrylamide, polyvinyl chloride, polyurethane) allows for immobilization under very mild conditions, preserving the integrity of living cells [4, 15]. A widely used carrier for microorganism immobilization is Sirane, which consists of porous silica glass beads with granule and pore sizes of 2–3 mm and 60–300 μm , respectively. The intensification of biocatalysis in immobilized cells is based on specific conditions that arise at the liquid-solid phase interface. It is assumed that this interface acts as a microenvironment where cells can more easily adjust their living conditions to a more favorable state.

Modern biotechnological processes effectively utilize immobilization methods on solid contact surfaces. The fundamental idea behind using immobilized microorganisms is that under such conditions, their biological activity is preserved significantly longer than that of intact cells [16]. This is explained by improved nutrient transport to the cells, which leads to intensified cellular metabolism.

Despite the positive aspects of immobilizing biological substances, including microbial cells, desorption (i.e., the release of bound microorganisms due to electropositive and electronegative interactions) is of great importance. The released microbial cells must retain their original biochemical survival properties and synthetic capabilities.

Therefore, the desorbing eluents used for immobilized cells and biological substances must be mild, harmless, and, most importantly, non-toxic. Consequently, this study is dedicated to selecting optimal conditions (time and volume) for desorbing immobilized bacterial cells using eluents.

The aim of this study is to investigate the conditions and degree of desorption of the *E. coli* ATCC 25922 strain immobilized on solid carriers prepared by micro-arc oxidation of aluminum oxide: AlMg6, ZnAl, and D16.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Required Consumables:

- 0.5 M and 1.0 M NaCl solution
- 0.5 N Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.0
- Endo-agar medium
- MPA-agar medium

Research Objects: The immobilized *E. coli* ATCC 25922 culture on ceramic-coated samples of AlMg6, ZnAl, and D16 alloys.

For the experiments, pre-prepared and sterilized nutrient media were poured into 200 mL conical flasks and then distributed in 20 mL portions into sterilized Petri dishes.

The 0.5 M and 1.0 M NaCl solutions were prepared according to the standard formulation and sterilized in an autoclave at 120°C for 30 minutes.

The desorption of *Escherichia coli* bacterial cells was carried out stepwise by adding the desorbing solutions to the sorbents under sterile conditions, followed by shaking on a rocker for 10 minutes at room temperature.

After each elution with the desorbing solution, the number of desorbed cells in 0.1 mL of eluate was determined by cultivating them on solid MPA (HiMedia) nutrient medium at 37°C for 6–12 hours. The resulting colonies (CFU/mL) on Petri dishes were counted visually using arithmetic calculations and also using a Goryaev chamber. This method allows for live bacterial cell observation and quantitative analysis, providing the number of microorganisms per unit volume (CFU/mL) in the desorption eluates.

Desorption was performed using a 0.5–1.0 M NaCl solution with a pH of 7.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The ceramic-coated samples of AlMg6, ZnAl, and D16 alloys selected for immobilization differed from each other in the presence of microscopic pores and immobilization efficiency (Table 1).

Table 1

The number of immobilized Escherichia coli ATCC 25922 cells on solid carriers.

Carrier samples	Initial cell count (million)	Cell count in solution after sorption,	Number of adsorbed cells,	Wash with NaCl,	Number of sorbed cells on the carrier,	% sorption.
AlMg6	70 312 500	34 375 000	35 937 500	74 800	35 862 700	51,0
D16		33 125 000	37 187 500	47 450	37 140 050	52,82
*ZnAl		53 125 000	43 750 000	47 800	43 702 200	62,15

For the desorption of immobilized *Escherichia coli* bacterial cells specified in Table 1, a 0.5 M NaCl solution with a pH of 7.0 was used in a sterile box at room temperature (24°C) with shaking for 5 minutes. The elution process was continued until the amounts of adsorbed cells specified in Table 1 were released.

The number of released bacterial cells was determined by plating each batch of eluate onto the selective MPA medium and counting the number of colonies grown on the surface of the Petri dish. Additionally, the number of cells in the eluate was counted using a Goryaev chamber (Table 2).

Thus, after elution of the sorbent, the release efficiency of immobilized cells into the eluate solution was determined using the method of plating 0.1 ml of the eluate onto a solid nutrient medium with MPA in Petri dishes. The growth of desorbed cells was then observed by incubating the plated samples at 37°C in a thermostat for 6–12 hours.

The stages of desorption and colony growth indicators (*cells/ml*) of *E. coli* in the eluate solution are shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3.

<i>Multiplicity (1-5) of elution and growth of desorbed cells on MPA, CFU/mL.</i>				
1	2	3	4	5
<i>Number of grown colonies contained in eluates (1-5) of desorption, CFU/mL.</i>				
141	260	240	67	112
<i>Multiplicity (6-10) of elution and growth of desorbed cells on MPA, CFU/mL.</i>				
6	7	8	9	10
<i>Number of grown colonies contained in eluates (6-10) of desorption, CFU/mL.</i>				
47	58	6	22	3

Fig. 1. Indicators of desorbed *E. coli* cells immobilized on the ZnAl adsorbent sample.

As seen from the data in Figure 1, in a volume of 100 ml, almost all adsorbed *E. coli* cells were desorbed from the ZnAl adsorbent. At the final stage of elution, only three bacterial colonies were detected as released from the sorbent, indicating the successful release of the immobilized culture cells.

The stages of desorption from the AlMg6 adsorbent and the colony growth indicators of *E. coli* (CFU/ml) in the eluate solution, detected at each repetition, are shown in Figure 2.

After 10 consecutive washes of the AlMg6 sorbent with adsorbed bacterial cells under shaking conditions at room temperature, 38 bacterial colonies were detected in the final eluate.

At the next stage, the desorption of immobilized bacterial cells from the D16 sorbent was also carried out under similar conditions using 0.5 M NaCl. The stages of desorption from the D16

adsorbent and the colony growth indicators (*CFU/ml*) of *E. coli* in the eluate solution are shown in Fig. 3.

<i>Multiplicity (1-5) of elution and growth of desorbed cells on MPA, CFU/mL.</i>				
1	2	3	4	5
<i>Number of grown colonies contained in eluates (1-5) of desorption, CFU/mL.</i>				
300	100	64	120	76
<i>Multiplicity (6-10) of elution and growth of desorbed cells on MPA, CFU/mL.</i>				
6	7	8	9	10
<i>Number of grown colonies contained in eluates (6-10) of desorption, CFU/mL.</i>				
73	52	67	59	38

Fig. 2. Indicators of desorbed *E. coli* cells immobilized on the AlMg6 adsorbent sample

<i>Multiplicity (1-5) of elution and growth of desorbed cells on MPA, CFU/mL.</i>				
1	2	3	4	5
<i>Number of grown colonies contained in eluates (1-5) of desorption, CFU/mL.</i>				
296	296	182	168	146
<i>Multiplicity of elution (6-10) of sorbed cells and growth on MPA, CFU/mL.</i>				
6	7	8	9	10
<i>Number of grown colonies contained in eluates (6-10) of desorption, CFU/mL.</i>				
120	110	83	54	41

Fig. 3. Indicators of desorbed *E. coli* cells immobilized on the D16 adsorbent sample

After the desorption process and the completion of elution, it was found that the number of desorbed cells immobilized on the three carrier samples varied. The most efficient desorption was observed with the ZnAl sorbent, reaching up to 74.36% after 10 elution cycles over 50 minutes (Table 2).

Table 2. Comparative evaluation of the desorption of immobilized *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 culture cells on various solid sorbents.

Carrier samples	initial cell count (million)	number of immobilized cells	% adsorption	elution volume for desorption (mL)	number of desorbed cells	% desorption
ZnAl	70 312 500	43 702 200	62,15	100	32 496 955	74,36
AlMg6		37 140 050	52,82	120	24 798 411	66,77
D16		35 862 700	51,0	100	21 915 695	61,11

The desorption of immobilized bacterial cells from the AlMg6 carrier was 66.77%, whereas for the D16 carrier, the number of desorbed cells was 61.11%.

Thus, the obtained results demonstrated that the desorption of immobilized bacterial cells using 0.5 M NaCl varied depending on the carriers and the number of elution cycles.

The ceramic coating samples in the AlMg6, ZnAl, and D16 alloys proved to be highly suitable sorbents for preserving immobilized *Escherichia coli* cells. The characteristics of the ceramic coating in the D16 alloy sample indicated that it retains bacterial cells more effectively than the AlMg6 and ZnAl samples, likely due to the strong binding of cells to the functional groups of the sorbent.

The ceramic coating in the D16 alloy sample can be used not only for storing *Escherichia coli* bacterial cells but also for preserving cells of other microorganisms.

The conducted experiments showed that the desorption process should be continued using desorbing agents with high ionic strength and optimized conditions to achieve the complete release of immobilized bacterial cells from the carriers used.

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